

RETHINKING DATA AND DATA PRACTICE IN FOOD SYSTEMS FOR ECOLOGICAL FUTURES

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ABSTRACT

Notions of data are increasingly bound to digital databases and underlying technologies that remove data from the material world in which it is captured - and therefore from more complex social and environmental contexts. In my PhD, I argue that such notions can be problematic, as they interpret reality into fixed forms of representation and limit our ability to retain a changing and evolving reality that extends and impacts the more-than-human world. The research seeks to unpack the representational tendencies of data science and look at alternative notions of data and data practice in order to acknowledge more inclusive ‘ecological dimensions’, which comprise a wide range of heterogeneous and local data sources created, not only by humans and machines, but also plants, animals, and minerals.

SUMMARY OF MY PHD PROJECT

This project aims to problematize the prevailing concepts of data and explore an alternative concept of data and data practices in a food systems context.

“How can design help to rethink data and data practice to embrace cultural and ecological values?”

This broad question is broken down into more specific questions:

RQ1: How might we translate the physical world into data more culturally and ecologically?

RQ2: What kinds of new mindsets and practices are required for the data?

RQ3: What would the ecological futures look like if we manifest the new concept of data and data practices?

In order to carry out an in-depth investigation on RQ1 and RQ2, I undertook fieldwork in small and urban farming areas in Amsterdam to learn how urban farmers interpret data from nature (i.e., humans, non-humans, the environment) through daily practice and experience for pursuing cultural and ecological values. The insights were turned into a framework that is a crucial element in developing a design probe and a workshop. To answer RQ3, I will explore tomatoes as relational and embodied data as evidence of ‘intra-acting’ between human and non-human entities. A speculative approach leads to recontextualising objectified tomatoes by reconnecting them with entities that have meaningful relationships in a specific time and space and envisioning how meanings of the relationships might be changed/evolved with future-driven natural (e.g., climate change), social (e.g., human-free farm), and technological (e.g., gene editing) factors.

CONTRIBUTION

My participation in the DC can contribute to rethinking the onto-epistemology of data with practice-based research to tangibly explore relationality, entanglement, and embodiment of them in a real-life context. It would offer new ways to explore expanded notions of data through a design practice for a more-than-human world.

NEXT STEPS

I am in the 2nd year of my PhD. This year, I will create design artefacts and organize speculative participatory workshops to engage stakeholders (scientists, farmers,

chefs, and civil servants) in food systems with an iterative design process. I expect my PhD research will provide more tangible and place-based examples to unpack challenges and opportunities in the relationship between data, humans and non-humans, and the environment from an ecological perspective.